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An assessment of the effect of training and development on employee performance: A review perspective

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Abstract

Training is generally considered as tool which is used to enhance individual skills, knowledge and abilities of a resource, and to enable that person to understand certain aspects of business. Training and Resource Development, when combined together with other practices directly affect the quality of HR outcomes, which eventually results in firm's higher performance. Need for a training program arises whenever there is a gap between the desired and actual performance of the employees. Usually the senior management of a company tries to fill this skill gap by opting for 'On-job training'. Training is defined as 'Planned intervention that is designed to enhance the determinants of individual job performance' Training sessions help employees in reducing frustration and anxiety which is created by heavy workloads and also enables them to handle this effectively. Modern organizations have realized the importance of Human Resource Development (HRD), and have begun to use on-job training as a tool for increasing employee satisfaction. It is indeed the responsibility of the senior management of any organization to understand not only the apparent but also the 'hidden' needs of their employees. Generally are three types of trainings: On-Job training, Off-Job Training, and apprenticeship training. It is against this backdrop that this study intends to explore the essence of training and development on employee performance.

Keywords: Training; Development; Performance; Organization

1. Introduction

According to Kulkarni (2013), different practices are followed in different industries and in different organizations too. So, the need of training and development programs is depending up on the requirements of the job profile, there are various types of programs shared by different authors. The types of training and development programs are as follows: On the Job Training and Off the Job Training. The On the Job Training comprise of job instructions, Apprenticeship and Coaching, Job Rotation, Committee Assignment, Internship Training and Training through step by step. However, Off The Job Training on the other hands includes programmed instructions, Class Room Lectures, Simulation Exercises, Business Games, Case Study Methods, Audio Visual Method, Experimental Exercises, Vestibules training, Computer Modelling, Behaviour Modelling, Role Playing, Conference/ Discussion Method and Workshop/ Seminar.

On the job training relates to formal training on the job. It's used to acquire specific skills while employee is on the job. The employee learns as he works under the method. The learning by doing approach is employed, and an employee become more experience on the job over time due to job behavior modification at the point of training. This type of training is usually done under established standards (Vaught, Hoy and Buchana, 1985) Human resource development focuses on the training to solve organizational issues and develop technical knowledge, interpersonal skills, social dealing and other skills set of its employees (Kuchinke, 1996). On the job training are commonly used for educating the

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employees of organization at all level. The aim of this training is get aware the employees with new practices or promote the skills of the workers related to a specific job. This type of training is usually done under established standards (Vaught, Hoy and Buchana, 1985). Common methods of include job rotation, coaching and assignments. Both of the methods are applied to the employees in order to learn technical and managerial skills. Skills needed to problem solving and interpersonal are mostly obtained effectively and efficiently by the employees through On the Job training (VanWart, Cayer and Cork, 2000)

Off the job training involves professional training given to employees, according to Nwachukwu (2000) Thus also known as vestibule training, and in this training, the trainee is not in the regular job environment, but it taught how to do his job in an identical situation using the same kind of equipment that he/she will use at the job site. One of the advantages is that costly mistake are avoided and the problem of transfer of training is enhanced as the trainees practice with identical equipment and tools. Off the job training include conference, role playing lectures, sensitivity training, workshop, seminars, computer-based training, business games, etc.

Apprenticeship training: - For a nation to progress socially and experience technological growth, emphasis should be placed on the development of man who is responsible for the transformation of the resources. It is a recognized fact that for any sustainable development, investment in man is superior and more durable than any infrastructural development or the building of machine.

Apprenticeship may be considered as a system of learning where by individual learn a professional skill in a practical way through a structured program on the job training. It usually involves acquiring knowledge, mechanical skills and the development of an attitude or discipline for a particular job. Craig and Bittel (1967) opined that, apprentice is a combination of on the job training and related technical instruction in which workers learn the practical and theoretical aspect of a skill occupation, craft or trade. Anyanwu (1981) expatiated further that apprentice may also take the form of helping new employees to relate their new job. Apprenticeship also incorporates a system of guidance and counselling as most apprentices are required to live with their masters so as to acquire through a process of acculturation the necessary altitude, diplomacy and decorum required for the job.

Curriculum, on the hand, may be operationally defined as the program of training through which learners pass to an intended goal. This means that all the activities done by the apprentice or experiences acquired by him in or outside the workshop under the guidance of his master constitute his training program and thus his curriculum.

Employee Productivity is the log of net sales over total employees - an economic measure of output per unit of input. Employee productivity measures may be examined collectively (across the whole economy) or viewed industry by industry. The Oxford dictionary defines 'productivity' as the state of producing rewards or results. 'Productive' means fruitful, lucrative and profitable.

Training has been an important variable in increasing organizational productivity. Most of researches including Colombo and Stanca (2008), Sepulveda (2005) and Konings & Vanormelingen, (2009), showed that training is a fundamental and effectual instrument in successful accomplishment of the firm's goals and objectives, resulting in higher productivity. Training design refers to the degree to which the training has been designed and delivered in such a way that provides trainees the ability to transfer learning back to the job (Holton, 2000). Holton further argues that part of transfer design is the degree to which training instructions match job requirements. It is observed that investigation directed at building a contingency model of transfer-oriented training intervention design would provide information important for developing training environments more conducive to positive transfer in terms of productivity effectiveness. Identification of training needs, design and implementation of training programmes, transfer of training, and evaluation of program's benefits are critical activities to the success of the undertaking (Krishnaveni & Sripirabaa, 2008) in addition to studying general training variables such as types of training, selection of trainees, selection criteria, evaluation instruments etc. The success of training depends on the correct implementation of all steps of the process; previous analysis of training needs development and implementation of an adequate training plan and evaluation (Mirabet, 1997). To sum it up, it's imperative for us to conclude that training together with other activities positively affects results and is associated with a productivity increase and a staff turnover decrease (Arthur, 1994). However, despite the significance of both the training needs analysis, which influences the development, application and evaluation of training and the plan development and implementation stage where the training characteristics are established and put into practice is also very important.(Frazis,2000).

Caruth & Handlogten, (2001) states that: "Employees are motivated when there are financial rewards directly tied to their performance". Employees receive compensation from a company in return for work performed. Compensation and pay are not the same; the fact is that compensation is much more than just the monetary rewards provided by an

employer. According to Milkovitch & Newman, (2005), in Compensation, it is "all forms of financial returns and tangible services and benefits employees receive as part of an employment relationship". The term "financial returns" refers to an individual's base salary, as well as short- and long-term incentives. "Tangible services and benefits" are the things such as insurance, paid vacation and sick days, pension plans, and employee discounts.

This is in contrast with development, which is training that provides employees with competencies for anticipated future jobs and roles. The goal of training is for employees to master the knowledge, skill, and behaviours emphasized in training programs and to apply them to their day-to-day activities. Recently it has been acknowledged that to impart a competitive advantage, training has to involve more than just basic skill development. That is, to use training to gain a competitive advantage, companies should view training broadly as a way to create intellectual capital. Intellectual capital includes basic skills (skills needed to perform one's job), advanced skills (such as how to use technology to share information with other employees) and understanding of the customer or manufacturing system, and self-motivated creativity. But some researchers estimated that soon up to 85 percent of jobs in Canada, the United States, and Europe will require extensive use of knowledge. This requires employees to share knowledge and creatively use it to modify a product or serve the customer, as well as to understand the service or product development system. The impressive economic development patterns of these countries can thus be credited to the important role that its human resources have played. Identification of training needs, if done properly provides the basis on which all other training activities can be considered. It is also a process that requires a careful thought and analysis, as training is a sensitive issue to people's lives whilst taking into account the reputation of the organization.

Training has the distinct role in the achievement of an organizational goal by incorporating the interests of organization and the workforce (Stone 2002). An employee is one of the most essential resource and an important asset in any organization. According to a recent industry report by the American Society for Training and Development (ASTD), U.S. organizations alone spend more than \$126 billion annually on employee training and development (Paradise 2007). There are various human resource functions that give an organization a competitive edge but most scholars argue that human resource functions becomes only operational when training has run through them all. This places training and development as an essential function in the survival of any organization. Employee performance depends on many factors like job satisfaction, knowledge and management but there is relationship between training and performance (Chris Amisano, 2010). Increasingly, high performing organizations today are recognizing the need to use best training and development practices to enhance their competitive advantage. Training and development are an essential element of every business if the value and potential of its people is to be harnessed and grown. The implementation of training and development programs are critical factors that most organizations need in order to enhance employee performance. Therefore, for effective use of human resource the level of training and skills of an employee is very critical for any organization. Companies can reap the rewards of providing training to their employees because well-trained workers help increase productivity and profits. Investing in employee training is always geared towards enhancing worker retention rates, customer satisfaction and creativity for new product ideas. Effective training saves labor by reducing time spent on problem-solving and saves money in the long run by producing a better workforce.

Training is necessary to ensure an adequate supply of staff that is technically and socially competent and capable of career development geared towards helping organizations realize their vision. In the contemporary dynamic corporate world, employees are increasingly required to keep up to the upcoming changes. Training is important for employees' development as it enables them achieve self-fulfilling skills and abilities, reduce operational costs, limits organizational liabilities (Donald, 2009). Properly trained employees are highly motivated and have more sense of responsibility hence requiring less supervision which in-turn increases the organization's ability in attaining its mission. The study will principally focus on the effect of training and development on employee performance and productivity.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Training

Training is a part of Human resources development (HRD). Human resource development is related to individual and team well-being, concerned with training, development and education. Variables arguably also indirectly related to job HRD has been defined as an organized learning practice performance conducted in a specific time period, to increase the skills of the employees and their capability and opportunity of improving job performance. Training is defined as learning that is provided in order to improve the performance on the present job (Nadler and Leonard, 1984)

Training is a systematic development of the knowledge, skills and behavior required by employees to do adequately on confirmed task or job. It can take place in numerous ways, on the job or off the job; in the organization or outside

organization. Training enhances knowledge and information about a certain field and also adds advantage to networking for efficiency.

Some authors use the terms “training” and “development” as synonyms. However, some view the two concepts as being different. Jones, George and Hill, (2000) believe that training primarily focuses on teaching organisational members how to perform their current jobs and helping them acquire the knowledge and skills they need to be effective performers.

Training is different from education. Training teaches the learner how to do a specific task, such as running a machine, or making a shirt. Education is instruction in the more general knowledge of the society, such as the history of the society, or knowledge of mathematics. As societies developed, there accumulated more knowledge than people could pick up on their own or learn informally from others.

At some point it became necessary to formally educate young people in the amassed knowledge of their society in order to help them function in that society.

Development on the other focuses on building the knowledge and skills of organisational members so that they will be prepared to take on new responsibilities and challenges.

In the view of Adamolekun (1983), staff development involves the training, education and career development of staff members. The purpose of training and development has been identified to include: creating a pool of readily available and adequate replacements for personnel who may leave or move up in the organization; enhancing the company’s ability to adopt and use advances in technology because of a sufficiently knowledgeable staff; building a more efficient, effective and highly motivated team, which enhances the company’s competitive position and improves

employee morale; and ensuring adequate human resources for expansion into new programs (<http://www.zeromillion.com/business/personnel/employee-training.html> accessed on 31st May, 2014 at 1220hrs). As a way of summary, the purpose of training is to improve knowledge and skills and to change attitude (Mullins, 1999). Mullins argues further that training is capable of producing the following benefits:

- Increase the confidence, motivation and commitment of staff;
- Provide recognition, enhanced responsibility, and the possibility of increased pay and promotion;
- Give feeling of personal satisfaction and achievement, and broaden opportunities for career progression; and
- Help to improve the availability and quality of staff. Hence, training helps employees do their current jobs, development prepares individuals to handle future responsibilities. Training increases productivity, reduces the level of supervision required, reduces accidents related to work and increases organization stability.

An employee who takes part in the organization’s training and development program also benefits from the program. A well-managed training function leads an employee to perform his/ her job better, improves his/ her job knowledge and performance, and prepares him/ her for a transfer and promotion from within. The program enables the employee to change his/ her environment and thus gathering fresh vigor for working, improves employee attitudes and loyalty to the work organization. It also helps a person develop his or her speaking, listening and writing skills. Further, a well-managed training helps the employee adjust to change, improve his or her self-confidence, increase job satisfaction and recognition, satisfies the personal needs of

The trainee and eliminates the employee’s fear in attempting new tasks (Ngirwa, 2005:288-289).

Often, organizations intend to retain their work force for long time in order to utilize the human resources, since they commit huge investments in them. Training and development cost enormous sums of money. Examples of training costs include; salaries, wages and benefits of training officers, part of managers’ salaries, wages and benefits for the period of coaching staff, capital cost of setting up the organization’s training centers and running costs of the training centers. Others include training aids like projectors, films, books, servicing for the above mentioned equipment, consultation fees and training fees paid to the institutions where organization’s employees are enrolled

2.2. Training and Development (T&D) Methods

Most of the government’s service delivery is provided through people, directly and indirectly. The success of an organization, its customers’ satisfaction and its efficiency depend heavily on its employees’ skills, abilities, knowledge and motivation to work. Investment in people development particularly in focused skills is no longer a choice. The

desired improvement and change required can more likely be achieved by improving the capacity and capability of the people who deliver the services. Having a structured approach to building the capacity of the workforce will therefore continue to positively impact and improve the services delivered to the community.

Efficiency and effectiveness of an organization depends directly on how capable its personnel are and how effectively their utilized for achieving organizational objectives.

According to Chandrasekha, B.V.N.G. (2011) there are several T&D methods available. The use of a particular method depends which method accomplishes the training needs and objectives. Training methods can be classified into two categories:

2.3. On-the-Job Methods

This refers to the methods of training in which a person learns a job by actually doing/performing it. A person works on a job and learns and develops expertise at the same time. The company does not have to arrange for special training other than to assign an experienced worker to train an inexperienced one. It may not be the most effective or the most efficient method. So long as the training takes place on the job, no transfer of learning is required.

2.4. Understudy

In this the employee is trained by his or her supervisor. The trainee is attached with his or her senior and called understudy or assistant. For example, a future manager might spend few months as assistant to the present manager.

2.4.1. Job Rotation

This refers to shifting/movement of an employee from one job to another on regular intervals. Hence, this is where the trainee is given several jobs in succession, to gain experience of a wide range of activities (e.g. a graduate management trainee might spend periods in several different departments).

2.4.2. Special projects

The trainees' may ask to work on special projects related with departmental objectives. By this, the trainees will acquire the knowledge of the assigned work and also learn how to work with others. In this employees join a project team – which gives them exposure to other parts of the business and allow them to take part in new activities. Most successful project teams are "multi-disciplinary".

2.4.3. Experience

It refers to learning by doing. This is one of the oldest methods of on-the-job training. Although this is very effective method but it also very time-consuming and wasteful. Thus it should be followed by other training methods.

2.4.4. Committee assignment

In this, the trainees become members of a committee. The committee is assigned a problem to discuss and make recommendations.

2.4.5. Coaching

Is a teaching or training process in which an individual gets support, while learning to achieve a specific personal or professional result or goal. The individual getting coached may be referred to as the client, the mentee or coachee or they may be in an intern or apprenticeship with the person coaching them.

In this, the supervisor or the superior acts as a guide and instructor of the trainee. This involves extensive demonstration and continuous critical evaluation and correction. This is a more intensive method of training that involves a close working relationship between an experienced employee and the trainee

2.4.6. Off-the-Job Methods

These methods require trainees to leave their workplace and concentrate their entire time towards the training objectives. These days' off-the-job training methods have become popular due to limitations of the on-the-job training methods such as facilities and environment, lack of group discussion and full participation among the trainees from different disciplines, etc. Determining who will practice as the trainer and what methods will be used are difficult decisions.

Hence, this is provided away from the immediate workplace. Thus might be at a specialist training centre or at a college or at a company's own premises. Thus type of training can be particularly use put for developing transferable skills that can be used in many different parts of the business. It may be used for example to train employees in the use of new equipment and new method or to bring them up to date with changes in the law.

Sound learning principles should always be used. The trainer should have knowledge of such learning principles as feedback, transfer of learning, whole versus partial learning and motivation. Feedback is necessary for learning to occur, individuals learn faster when they receive immediate feedback on their performances. In the off the- job methods, the development of trainees is the primary task rest everything is secondary. Following are the main off-the-job training methods:

2.4.7. Special Courses and Lectures

These are the most traditional and even famous today, method of developing personnel. Special courses and lectures are either designed by the company itself or by the management/professional schools. Companies then sponsor their trainees to attend these courses or lectures. These are the quick and most simple ways to provide knowledge to a large group of trainees. . Hence, these are the quick and most simple ways to provide knowledge to a large group of trainees. This approach is well adapted to convey specific information, rules, procedures and methods, this method is very useful where the information need to be shared among a large number of trainees. In this method cost per trainee is low.

2.5. Conferences and Seminars

In this, the participants are required to pool their thoughts, ideas, viewpoints, suggestions and recommendations. By attending conferences and seminars, trainees try to look at a problem from different angles as the participants are normally from different fields and sectors.

2.5.1. Selected Reading

This is the self-improvement training technique. The persons acquire knowledge and awareness by reading various trade journals and magazines. Most of the companies have their own libraries. The employees become the members of the professional associations to keep abreast of latest developments in their respective fields.

2.5.2. Case Study Method

This technique was developed by Harvard Business School, U.S.A. It is used as a supplement to lecture method. A case is a written record of a real business situation/problem faced by a company. The case is provided to the trainees for discussion and analysis. Identification and diagnose of the problem is the aim in case study method. Alternate courses of action are suggested from participants. This also present an in depth description of a particular problem an employee might encounter on the job. The employee attempts to find and analyze the problem, evaluate alternative courses of action & decide what course of action would be most satisfactory.

2.5.3. Programmed Instruction/Learning

This is step-by-step self-learning method where the medium may be a textbook, computer or the internet. This is a systematic method for teaching job skills involving presenting questions or facts, allowing the person to respond and giving the learner immediate feedback on the accuracy of his or her answers."

2.5.4. Brainstorming

This is creativity-training technique, it helps people to solve problems in a new and different way. In this technique, the trainees are given the opportunity to generate ideas openly and without any fear of judgments. Criticism of any idea is not allowed so as to reduce inhibiting forces. Once a lot of ideas are generated then they are evaluated for their cost and feasibility.

2.5.5. Role-Playing

In this method, the trainees are assigned a role, which they have to play in an artificially created situation. For example, a trainee is asked to play the role of a trade union leader and another trainee is required to perform the role of a HR manager. This technique results in better understanding of each other's situation by putting foot in other's shoes.

Here trainee act out a given role as they would in stage play. Two or more trainees are assigned roles in a given situation which is explained to the group. There are no written lines to be said and naturally no rehearsals. The role players have

to quickly respond to the situation that is ever changing and to react to it as they would in the real one. It is a method of human interaction which involves realistic behavior in an imaginary or hypothetical situation. Role playing primarily involves employee – employer relationships, hiring, firing, discussing a grievance problem, conducting a post appraisal interview, disciplining a subordinate, or a salesman making presentation to a customer.

2.5.6. Vestibule Schools

Large organizations frequently provide what are described as vestibule schools a preliminary to actual shop experience. As far as possible, shop conditions are duplicated, but instruction, not output is major objective. A vestibule school is operated as a specialized endeavor by the personnel department. Vestibule training creates a miniature of the department for which the training program is carried on. It utilizes machinery similar to that in operation on the production floor. Qualified instructors, usually highly skilled operators or supervisors, are provided to conduct the program in this special section. Here the new employees are given a course of training in the particular machines they will be required to use and on the exact work they will do when they become a part of the regular production force This training is required when the amount of training that has to be done exceeds the capacity of the line supervisor; a portion of training is evolved from the line and assigned to staff through a vestibule school." The advantage of a vestibule school is specialisation.

2.5.7. Apprenticeship Training

This training approach began in the Middle Ages when those who wanted to learn trade skill bound themselves to a master craftsman and worked under his guidance. Apprenticeship training is a structured process by which people become skilled workers through a combination of classroom instruction and on-the-job training.

2.5.8. In-Basket Exercise

In this technique, the trainees are provided background information on a simulated firm and its products, and key personnel. After this, the trainees are provided with inbasket of memos, letters, reports, requests and other documents related with the firm. The trainee must make sense out of this mass of paperwork and prepare memos, make notes and delegate tasks within a limited time period. Also known as In-tray method of training. The trainee is presented with a pack of papers and files in a tray containing administrative problems and is asked to take decisions on these problems within a stipulated time. The decisions taken by the trainees are compared with one another. The trainees are provided feedback on their performance.

2.5.9. Business Games

Business games involve teams of trainees. The teams discuss and analyse the problem and arrive at decisions. Generally, issues related with inventories, sales, R&D, production process, etc. are taken up for consideration.

The trainees are divided into groups which represent the management of competing companies. They make decisions just like these which are made in real-life situations. Decisions made by the groups are evaluated and the likely implications of the decisions are fed back to the groups. The game goes on in several rounds to take the time dimension into account.

2.5.10. Behaviour Modeling

This is structured approach to teach specific supervisory skill. This is based on the social learning theory in which the trainee is provided with a specific model of behaviour and is informed in advance of the consequences of engaging in that type of behaviour.

2.5.11. Sensitivity (T-group) Training

In this type of training, a small group of trainees consisting of 10 to 12 persons is formed which meets in an unstructured situation. There is no set agenda or schedule or plan. The main objectives are more openness with each other, increased listening skills, trust, support, tolerance and concern for others. The trainers serve a catalytic role. The group meets in isolation without any formal agenda. There is great focus on inter-personal behaviour. And, the trainer provides honest but supportive feedback to members on how they interacted with one another.

2.5.12. Multiple Management

This technique of training was first introduced by McCormick, President of McCormick & co. of Baltimore in 1932. He gave the idea of establishing a junior board of directors. Authority is given to the junior board members to discuss any

problem that could be discussed in senior board and give recommendations to the senior board. Innovative and productive ideas became available for senior board. Hence, off the job training is conducted in a location specifically designated for

Training. It may be near the work place or away from work, at a special training center or a resort; conducting the training away from the work place minimize distractions and allows trainee to devote their full attention to the material being taught.

2.5.13. Off the job training methods

Sometimes the management may want employees to be trained quickly because there are critical tasks to be completed. It may wish to train a large number of employees at the same time under a single trainer. The main draw back in this method is that a trainee has to remember and transfer what was taught theoretically onto a real work environment. The trainee usually has to learn at his/her pace and frequently feedback is given and sometimes not immediately after learning (Sleight, 1993).

Even if off the job training has many limitations, still the method is widely employed. It is popular to send young men and women with managerial promises to executive training programs conducted by universities and other groups for additional training. In these seminars, the young manager rubs shoulder with managers from other companies and hears different viewpoints about various problems (Gunnigle, *ibid*).

Determining who will practice as the trainer and what methods will be used are difficult decisions. Sound learning principles should always be used. The trainer should have knowledge of such learning principles as feedback, transfer of learning, whole versus partial learning and motivation. Feedback is necessary for learning to occur, individuals learn faster when they receive immediate feedback on their performance (Gibson, *et al*, 1983).

Hence, training is an attempt to improve their current and future performance but the organization should keep a track on their performance after imparting them training it means training needs assessment it is a systematic process of altering the behavior of employees in a direction to achieve the organization's goals.

So it is sensible to utilize the trained employees for betterment of their organizations in order to realize the profits from the investments they committed. However, they should adopt retention strategies of their key staff. To assure the retention of workers in an organization, training and retraining is recommended as one of the methods that can be employed by any work organization.

Training is of growing importance to companies seeking to gain an advantage among competitors. There is significant debate among professionals and scholars as to the effect that training has on both employee and organizational goals. One school of thought argues that training leads to an increase in turnover while the other states that training is a tool that can lead to higher levels of employee retention (Colarelli & Montei, 1996; Becker, 1993). Regardless of where one falls within this debate, most professionals agree that employee training is a complex human resource practice that can significantly impact a company's success.

2.5.14. On the Job Training

Laing (2009) defines on the job training as an indicator to enhance superior skills, knowledge, capabilities and outlook of the employees that results in effective performance of the workers .On-the-job training is typically one-on-one instructional session designed to give an employee additional skills, tools and resources in performing a job more successfully. This training can be direct instruction between employer and employee, a classroom environment between an expert and a small employee unit or a simulation, such as computer and online training programs.

As on-the-job training is a considerable investment, companies and employees need to know the effects of it and decide whether the investments will be justified.

2.5.15. Employee Performance

Employees who are the most efficient are like to be they are motivate to perform medina (2002) this relationship mean that rewards and employee performance is expecting theory which means that employee are most to be motivated performance is more performance to receive the rewards

Employees are extremely motivated to monthly rewards. The Goal is to satisfy the social exchange process they contribute the efforts Kanfell (1990). Entiwistal (1987) is of the view that 96 employee perform feel them. Organizational rewards result motivated employee.

Some other views that recognition in pleasanter the organization favorable works environment motivated the employee Freedman (1978) as cited in Rizwan and Ali (2010). Employee are the important part of any organization increasing the performance they can be motivated through financial and non-financial benefits they can designing that you can says that composition is reward which is receiving by the employee to show their performance. Employee concentrated pay or wages and similar to non-monetary exchange for the employee performance(Holt,1993).Good organization are maintain to design and enable the organizations to attract the highly skilled and qualified employee retain and motivation towards objective and goals achieve and most employee getting is pay(Decenzo and Robbins,1999).If the employee free that they have not getting good salary they cooking for better employee dissatisfaction with the compensation towards goal attainment towards goals done to be lower .Dissatisfied employee increasing the turnover, Absents am and poor metal health(Welthel and Davis,1996).The main objective of compensation is that employee attracted to work and motivated good job for employee Davis(1996).

2.6. The Concept of Employee Performance

Performance refers to the degree of achievement of the goal as well as the range of measurements of efficiency in workplaces. In general, employee performance is indicated by data that represents effectiveness such as productivity, goal achievement levels, customer satisfaction index, and attachment. In the view of Putteril& Rohrer (2005), employee performance focuses directly on employee productivity by assessing the number of units of acceptable quality produced by an employee, within a specific time period. The success of business or an organization depends on employees' performance. One of the most effective ways to increase organizational performance and profit is to increase the performance of employees, from the lowest levels of the organization to the senior management levels. Performance improvement is not only a result of well-functioning system but also depends on effective human resource strategies that succeed in recruiting and maintaining a committed and motivated workforce (Al-Ahmadi, 2009). The dimensions of performance on which an employee is evaluated are called the criteria of evaluation Ivancevich, (2008). Opatha, (2010) suggested that several criteria becomes needed in order to evaluate job performance of an employee accurately. In the view of Mathis & Jackson (2006), the data or information that managers receive on how well employees are performing their jobs can be of three different types. Trait-based information, Behavior-based information, Result based information. Opatha (2010) indicated that trait-based information identifies a subjective character of the employee such as attitude, initiative or creativity. Behavior-based evaluations of job performance focus on what is included in the job itself (Mathis & Jackson, 2006). Results are outcomes produced by the employee. Result based information consider employee accomplishment. For jobs in which measurement is easy and obvious, a results-based approach works well (Opatha, 2010).

Individual work performance is an issue that has not only bothered companies all over the world but also fuelled a great deal of researching in the fields of management, occupational health, work and organizational psychology. Numerous studies on individual work performance have been conducted. However, different approaches of studying individual work performance circulate in today's literature. Whereas the field of management has primarily occupied itself with how one can make an employee as productive as possible, Work and organizational psychologists, on the other hand, have an interest in the influence of determinants, such as work engagement, job satisfaction, and personality, on individual work performance. Performance is associated with quantity of output, quality of output, timeliness of output, presence or attendance on the job, efficiency of the work completed and effectiveness of work completed (Mathis & Jackson 2009). According to Mooney (2009) performance is not only related to results but it also relates with activities and behaviours of employees that they adopted to achieve their given goals. The traditional view that employees were regarded as a cost to the organization has been sharply contrasted to a fresh approach to human capital by Poisat (2006). He argues that there exists compelling evidence why organizations need to engage their employees in order to improve their performance and hence significantly contribute to the organization's bottom line.

According to Van Dyk and Herholdt (2004) disputed the organizations claim that people are their greatest asset, and is convinced that, even though possibly subconsciously, the belief still exists that people need the organization more than it needs them. He argues that in fact, organizations and institutions have to market membership as much as, and perhaps more than, products and services. They asserted that institutions should attract people, retain people, recognize and reward people, motivate people, serve and satisfy people. Additionally, they argue that Performance is about behaviour or what employees do, not about what employees produce or the outcomes of their work. Perceived employee performance represents the general belief of the employee about his behaviour and contributions in the success of organization.

Employee performance may be taken in the perspective of three factors which makes possible to perform better than others, determinants of performance may be such as declarative knowledge, procedural knowledge and motivation (McCloy et al., 1994). Human Resource practices have positive impact on performance of individuals. Huselid (1995) argued that the effectiveness the HR practitioners will transfer on the behaviour of employees, which also proves a positive association. Teseema and Soeters (2006) have carried out study on eight HR practices including recruitment and selection practices, placement practices, training, compensation, employee performance evaluation, promotion, grievance procedure and pension or social security in relation with the perceived performance of employees. They concluded that these HR practices have positive and significant associations with the perceived performance of employees.

Employee satisfaction and retention have always been important issues for organizations and institutions of learning. High levels of absenteeism and staff turnover can affect the bottom line of the organization, as temps, recruitment and retraining take their toll. The term Employee Satisfaction refers to an individual's general attitude toward his or her job. A person with a high level of job satisfaction holds positive attitudes toward the job and tends to be more productive, creative and committed to their employers while a person who is dissatisfied with his or her job tends to hold negative attitudes about the job. Organizations that can create work environments that attract, motivate and retain hard-working individuals will be better positioned to succeed in a competitive environment that demands quality and cost-efficiency (Gibss, 2000).

According to Huselid (1995) recruitment procedures that provide a large pool of qualified applicants, paired with a reliable and valid selection regime, will have a substantial influence over the quality and type of skills new employees possess. An organization's human resource policies and practices represent important forces for shaping employee behaviour and attitudes. The selection practices will determine who is hired. If properly designed, it will identify competent candidates and accurately match them to the job. The use of the proper selection device will increase the probability that the right person is chosen to fill a slot. When the best people are selected for the job, productivity increases.

According to Robbins (2003), a dissatisfied employee can still be a loyal employee where such an employee will be passively waiting for conditions to improve. In addition, such an employee can also express their dissatisfaction by terminating their relationship with the organization, actively making their opinion heard in an attempt to improve matters, or by passively allowing conditions to worsen through neglect. He further emphasizes the importance of employee job satisfaction as a factor influencing, amongst others, employee work performance. He argues that happy workers aren't necessarily productive workers. This argument is in line with Poisat's deduction (2006) that satisfied employees are not necessarily productive employees.

He further suggests that the opposite might be more accurate; that productivity will probably lead to satisfaction. The enactment of the HRMP Act 2012 implies that HR practitioners adopt new approaches on employee recruitment and retention, training, compensation and performance and employee relations. These changes in the long run impacts on the job outcomes of the employees and the productivity of organizations.

2.7. Human Capital Theory

According to Shultz (1961), the human capita theory is significant in elucidating the prominence of marketable skills among workers which is held in form of capital that workers make a number of investments. Furthermore, Training and education need to be treated as investment in the person receiving it because it becomes part of the person receiving it (Shultz, 1961). The human capita theory is concerned with extend of stock of knowledge possessed by employees which distinguishes their performance from those of others. In addition, it emphasizes on the skills, knowledge and capabilities possessed by employees in a given organization (Odhiambo, 2018), people are worth investing in as a form of capital.

The human capital theory is one of the significant theories in economics that explains the importance of developing employee skills so as to make them more productive (Odhiambo, 2018). The theory maintains that investments are made in human resources development with the aim of improving their productivity (Odhiambo, 2018). Furthermore, improved productivity leads to improved earnings as the employers would always want to recognize well performing employees bearing unique and exceptional skills in whatever they are engaged to do (Nafukho, Hairston & Brooks, 2004). According to Becker (1993), who extended the definition of human capital to include the diversity of knowledge possessed, depth and suitability of ideas, depth of information, health of individual workers, skills diversity and flexibility. In contrast, Schultz (1961) who restricted the coverage of capital in workers, Becker (1993) includes health dimensions to human capital for the reason that unhealthy worker is likely to be less productive. According to Ployhart & Moliterno (2011), the coverage of human capital has developed ever since to incorporate the skills and expertise of

workers, combined intelligence, workers' performance, and their potential in the organization. Odhiambo (2018) further indicated that these distinctive employee dimensions that provide distinctive character to an organization which if well utilized could lead to achievement of sustainable competitive advantage. According to Ployhart et al. (2014), the result of human capital is manifested through employee productivity job performance.

In his study, Ngugi (2014) applied human capital theory to examine perceived relationship between training and development in employee performance using the case of Geothermal Development Company (GDC). His work described how well developed and equipped human resource can provide exemplary performance which can enable quality service delivery and overall customer satisfaction. Amadi (2014) also explained how training and development influences performance of workers at Safaricom Call Centre. In an organization, each job calls for a unique skills and expertise. This avails the right skills and expertise at the right time and in the right position. This provides the organization with a sustainable competitive advantage. Employee training tries to bridge the gap by bringing employees up to, but not beyond, the desired standard or competence (Odhiambo, 2018). The over-all investment in human capital generates in the labor-force that is skill-base. The relevancy of the human capital theory to the study of effect of training needs assessment on employee performance of selected tertiary institutions in Borno State, Nigeria is that design of training programs at the work place equips workers with vibrant skill and knowledge which permits them to be significant assets that aid sustainability of an organization (Odhiambo, 2018). The human capital theory is therefore appropriate in the study of Training and development on employee performance.

3. Conclusion

The study is significant because it will be useful immensely to staff training and development in the academic institutions across the country. It is also hoped to be useful to researchers, scholars and policy makers toward policy planning and implementation in the field of human resource development and for the promotion of efficient and effective workforce. In addition, this study will contribute to the existing knowledge or literature on human resource development and training for public servants.

The study will be important to students because Training will help students develop skills and abilities that support professional's studies, it also provides an opportunity to learn important skills which will help in becoming a professional of the future.

Furthermore, the study will benefit the Society as it will help in improving the level of performance and hence result in higher productivity. Uniformity of work method and procedures will help to improve the quality of product or service. It will also boost the morale to employees to perform the task/job efficiently and lower the rate of accident.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors report there is no competing interest to declare. The study is strictly our original work and has no conflict of interest whatsoever.

Statement of ethical approval

The research is not associated with any kind or form of radioactive elements or animal or human exposure in any laboratory. The study in it's entirety has no risk or threat factors. It is purely a social research, thus do not require ethical approval.

Statement of informed consent

The study is a review work and therefore does not require permission or statement of informed consent

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